

Synthesis and Physicochemical Properties of Three *meta*-substituted *meso*-tetraphenylporphyrins

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Three porphyrins, *meso*-tetra-*meta*-carbomethoxyphenylporphin (3-CO₂Me-TPP), *meso*-tetra-*meta*-cyanophenylporphin (3-CN-TPP) and *meso*-tetra-*meta*-carboxyphenylporphin (3-COOH-TPP) have been synthesized. Their electronic, infrared and proton magnetic resonance spectra determined.

RECENT studies have shown a number of interesting biochemical properties of *meso*-tetraphenylporphyrins and some of their metal complexes, viz., radiation modifying effects of metal chelates of *meso*-tetra(*p*-carboxyphenyl)porphin in human lymphoid cell line¹, selective distribution of porphyrins in tumor bearing mice², intercalation of porphyrins with DNA³, and inhibition of thrombin-induced polymerization of fibrinogen by porphyrins in presence and absence of light⁴. In order to reveal newer biochemical properties as well as to understand the ones already observed we have prepared a series of these porphyrins.

In this paper we report the synthesis, interconversion, and physicochemical properties of three porphyrins, viz., *meso*-tetra-*meta*-carbomethoxyphenylporphin (3-CO₂CH₃-TPP), *meso*-tetra-*meta*-cyanophenylporphin (3-CN-TPP) and *meso*-tetra-*meta*-carboxyphenylporphin (3-COOH-TPP).

Experimental

All solvents and reagents used were of spectroscopic quality. Pyrrole, 3-cyanobenzaldehyde and 3-carboxybenzaldehyde were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. 3-Carbomethoxybenzaldehyde was synthesized by esterification of 3-carboxybenzaldehyde with methanol in presence of catalytic amount of concentrated sulfuric acid. UV-visible absorption, infrared absorption (determined in KBr matrix) and proton magnetic resonance spectra (determined in d₆-DMSO with TMS as internal standard; chemical shifts expressed in δ units) were determined in Perkin-Elmer Model 202, Perkin-Elmer Model 467 and Varian XI 100 spectrometers respectively.

For analysis, the compounds were dried over phosphorus pentoxide for 18 hr at 100°/1 mm. Elemental analysis was done by Galbraith Laboratories, Inc., Knoxville, Tenn., U.S.A. The melting points were taken in Mel-Temp block and are uncorrected.

Preparation and interconversion of the three porphyrins: The synthesis of the porphyrins was

done with established procedure⁵. A mixture of freshly distilled pyrrole, 0.5 mole, one of the aldehydes (mentioned above), 0.5 mole and 1000 ml propionic acid was refluxed for 2 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with acetone and kept at room temperature overnight. The crude porphyrin was filtered and washed with cold acetone. Silica gel chromatography, with tetrahydrofuran as the eluting solvent, yielded pure porphyrins.

The cyanophenylporphin (3-CN-TPP) and the carbomethoxyphenylporphin (3-CO₂Me-TPP) were hydrolyzed to the corresponding carboxyphenylporphin (3-CO₂H-TPP) by refluxing with alkali (NaOH/H₂O/pyridine) for 24 hr, followed by evaporation of pyridine and acidification with glacial acetic acid. The esterification of 3-CO₂H-TPP was completed by refluxing with methanol containing catalytic amount of conc. H₂SO₄ for 48 hr.

- (I) : X = CN
(II) : X = CO₂H
(III) : X = CO₂Me

Meso-tetra-meta-cyanophenylporphin (I): m.p. 411° (dec.) (Found: C, 80.45; H, 3.62; N, 15.18; $C_{48}H_{26}N_8$ requires: C, 80.67; H, 3.64; N, 15.69%); $\lambda_{\max}^{CH_2Cl_2}$ ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$): 418 (486), 514 (19.0), 548 (6.2), 592 (5.8) and 652 (3.8) nm; ν_{\max} : 3300 (N-H) and 2225 (C≡N) cm^{-1} ; δ 8.84 (8H, s, *Ha*), 8.7 (4H, s, *Hb*), 8.5 and 8.3 (4H, d, each, $J=8Hz$, *Hc+Hd*), 8.0 (4H, t, $J=7.5Hz$, *He*) and -3.0 (2H, s, N-H) ppm.

Meso-tetra-meta-carboxyphenylporphin (II): m.p. 481° (dec.) (Found: C, 72.46; H, 3.83; N, 6.98; $C_{48}H_{30}N_4O_8$ requires: C, 72.91; H, 3.80; N, 7.09%); λ_{\max}^{THF} ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$): 416 (349), 512 (13.3), 548 (5.8), 592 (5.3) and 650 (4.0) nm; ν_{\max} : 3300 (N-H) and 1700 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ 8.71 (8H, s, *Ha*), 8.62 (4H, s, *Hb*), 8.36 and 8.29 (4H, d, each, $J=7Hz$, *Hc+Hd*) and 7.84 (4H, t, $J=7.5Hz$, *He*) ppm.

Meso-tetra-meta-carbomethoxyphenylporphin (III): m.p. 370° (dec.) (Found: C, 73.58; H, 4.51; N, 6.59; $C_{52}H_{38}N_4O_8$ requires: C, 73.76; H, 4.49; N, 6.62%); $\lambda_{\max}^{CH_2Cl_2}$ ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$): 418 (556), 518 (18.3), 550 (7.0); 594 (5.6) and 654 (5.1) nm; ν_{\max} : 3300 (N-H) and 1740 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ 8.66

(8H, s, *Ha*), 8.60 (4H, s, *Hb*), 8.35 and 8.30 (4H, d, each, $J=7Hz$, *Hc+Hd*), 7.85 (4H, t, $J=8Hz$, *He*) and 3.95 (12H, s, CO_2CH_3) ppm.

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